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Simplified Derivation of an Equation for Electroviscous Effect

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It appears to the author that the reasoning on the basis of which Street' derived an equation for electroviscous effect requires modification. Introducing such modification in Street's reasoning as is considered necessary an equation for electroviscous effect may be deduced in the following way.

Let us consider a suspension containing per cubic centimeter N uncharged spherical particles, each of radius a . During flow in a capillary there is relative movement between the liquid and the uncharged particles and let v be the relative velocity of a particle with respect to the liquid and F_2 the force per particle necessary to maintain this relative velocity (v). Now suppose that each particle of the suspension ionises and acquires a charge Q . Then to maintain the same relative velocity (v) of the charged particles an extra force F_1 per particle is necessary to overcome the drag which the oppositely charged layers of liquid exert on the particle.

Hence the total force (F) necessary to maintain the relative velocity (v) of a charged particle during flow is

$$F = F_2 + F_1 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

Let η and η_s denote respectively the viscosity of the same suspension when the particles are all uncharged and charged

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Then } \eta_s &= \frac{F}{6\pi a v} = \frac{F_2}{6\pi a v} + \frac{F_1}{6\pi a v} = \eta + \frac{QE}{6\pi a v} \quad \dots \quad (2) \\ &= \eta + \frac{NQ^2}{6\pi a K} \quad \dots \quad (2a) \end{aligned}$$

As has been shown by Street $F_1 = QE$ and $E = \frac{NQv}{K}$ where K is the specific conductivity of the suspension.

Now $Q^2 = (\zeta Da)^2$ and $N = \phi / \frac{4}{3}\pi a^3$, where ζ is the zeta-potential, D the dielectric constant and ϕ the volume fraction.

Substituting these values of Q^2 and N in equation (2a) and dividing both sides by η_0 the viscosity of the dispersion medium, we get

$$\eta_s/\eta_0 = \eta/\eta_0 + \frac{\phi}{2\eta_0 a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \quad \dots \quad (2b)$$

According to Einstein $\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 2.5\phi$.

It is to be noted that in Einstein's equation ϕ has to be multiplied by 2.5. Therefore, ϕ in $\frac{\phi}{2\eta_0 a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2$ is multiplied by 2.5 and equation (2b) is written as follows :

$$\eta_s/\eta_0 = 1 + 2.5\phi \left[1 + \frac{1}{2\eta_0 a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

The equation derived by Street' is as follows :

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_s/\eta &= 1 + 2.5\phi \left[1 + \frac{\phi}{2\eta a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2 \right] \quad \dots \quad (4) \\ &= 1 + K_1\phi + K_2\phi^2 \quad \dots \quad (4a) \end{aligned}$$

where $K_1 = 2.5$ and $K_2 = \frac{K_1}{2\eta a^2 K} \left(\frac{D\zeta}{2\pi} \right)^2$.

It is to be noted that Street's equation (4) or (4a) contains a term involving ϕ^2 which does not occur

in author's equation (3), besides η is different from η_0 .

Attention may be drawn to the fact that in the deduction of equation (3) 6π has been used in the frictional coefficient. Smoluchowski has used 4π in such cases. The conditions under which 6π or 4π can be used have been clarified by the researches of Henry^{2,3}, Overbeek⁴ and others. It is now known that when (ka) is large, i.e., for thin double layer and large particle size use of 4π in place of 6π is justified. Therefore, for large particle size and thin double layer, the factor 2 in $\frac{1}{2\eta_0 a^2 K} \left(\frac{D_s}{2\pi}\right)^2$

can be replaced by 4/3, i.e., 1.33. Hence for large particle size and thin double layer the difference between author's equation (3) and Smoluchowski's equation for electroviscous effect is reduced further.

It may be mentioned that according to Whitehead⁶ there is a simple algebraic error in Street's equation (4) and the corrected equation should be written as:—

$$\eta_s/\eta = (1 + 2.5\phi) \left[1 + \frac{\phi}{2\eta_0 a^2 K} \left(\frac{D_s}{2\pi}\right)^2 \right]$$

Stone-Masui and Watilou⁷ report that for charged monodisperse polystyrene latex, the values of K_2 determined experimentally do not agree with those calculated from Street's Theory.

As already pointed out the term $K_2\phi^2$ does not occur in author's equation which is meant for the first-order electroviscous effect only.

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